

Consumer Perceptions of Corporate Social Responsibility: Analyzing how CSR initiative influence brand reputation in Sri Lanka.

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Background Information

Consumer Perceptions of CSR in Sri Lanka

Consumer perceptions of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Sri Lanka have become increasingly significant, particularly in the context of multinational enterprises (MNEs) operating within the fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) sector.

Studies have shown that CSR initiatives have a notable impact on consumer purchase intentions through the mediation of brand image, brand attitude, and perceived quality[4]. This indicates that CSR practices can enhance the reputation of brands, thereby influencing consumer behavior positively.

However, while business organizations have shown considerable improvement in managing operations sustainably, the consumer segment in Sri Lanka has not been equally active in promoting sustainable consumption practices[5]. This discrepancy highlights a gap between corporate initiatives and consumer participation. Although there have been recent amendments to environmental protection laws and awareness programs aimed at consumers, the overall level of consumer engagement in sustainability remains low[5].

Moreover, research indicates that there is a significant gap in the level of consumer awareness and education regarding sustainability issues. A 2018 survey aimed at understanding Sri Lankan consumers' awareness and attitudes towards sustainable consumption revealed that many consumers lack the necessary information to make environmentally-friendly decisions[2][7]. The survey assessed attitudes towards

environmental protection and the willingness to consider sustainability during purchasing decisions, pointing out that further education and awareness programs are essential to bridge this gap[7].

Thus, while CSR initiatives by MNEs in the Sri Lankan FMCG sector have begun to shape consumer perceptions positively, there is still considerable work to be done to enhance consumer awareness and active participation in sustainability practices.

Impact of CSR Initiatives on Brand Reputation in Sri Lanka

CSR initiatives play a significant role in shaping brand reputation in Sri Lanka. Companies in developing countries, including Sri Lanka, often face a unique set of social and environmental challenges. In Sri Lanka, the emphasis on corporate social responsibility tends to lean more towards addressing social issues such as unemployment and poverty rather than environmental concerns[3][6]. This trend is more noticeable in locally owned companies compared to those with overseas ownership, possibly due to historical, cultural, and religious influences[6].

A study examining the CSR practices of the largest 200 companies listed on the Colombo Stock Exchange revealed that environmental activities are not as widely implemented as social engagements[3]. Corporate managers in Sri Lanka prioritize social issues, which indicates a strong commitment to addressing the immediate needs of their communities[6]. This focus on social responsibility can enhance a company's reputation among local consumers, who may value the efforts to improve social welfare over environmental sustainability.

CSR Communication Strategy

A well-crafted CSR communication strategy is essential for businesses aiming to enhance their brand reputation and foster positive relationships with consumers in Sri Lanka. Effective CSR communication involves several key elements, beginning with a clear understanding of the company's corporate purpose and its alignment with broader social and environmental goals[8]. This approach not only strengthens corporate culture but also helps in building unity among employees while fulfilling social and financial commitments.

The cornerstone of a robust CSR communication strategy is its alignment with the company's overall corporate communications plan[9]. This involves defining how the

company will communicate both internally with employees and externally with customers, investors, and other stakeholders. Such a comprehensive strategy ensures that CSR initiatives are seamlessly integrated into the broader communication framework, thereby reinforcing the company's brand image and reputation.

Sustainability communication, an integral part of CSR strategy, should be more than just a public relations exercise; it must reflect genuine commitments to ethical business practices and environmental management[10]. ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) communication plays a crucial role here, serving as a bridge between the company's sustainability efforts and its stakeholders. By focusing on basic principles and strategic stakeholder engagement, businesses can communicate their sustainability initiatives more effectively.

Moreover, modern consumers and employees are increasingly demanding holistic value from corporations, beyond mere economic contributions[11]. This shift necessitates that companies move away from a sole focus on profit maximization and consider long-term sustainable practices. Corporate philanthropy and CSR initiatives are effective ways for businesses to demonstrate their commitment to societal welfare, thereby enhancing their public image and stakeholder trust.

Social media platforms offer a powerful tool for communicating CSR efforts[12]. The strategy should include guidelines on post frequency, audience engagement, and impact measurement relative to other campaigns. Involving followers through interactive and transparent communication can significantly boost the effectiveness of CSR initiatives.

Finally, it is imperative that CSR strategies are goal-driven, achievable, and authentic[13]. High-profile commitments, like GM's vow to be carbon neutral by 2040 or Apple's \$100 million investment in racial equity, demonstrate the importance of ambitious yet attainable goals. These commitments resonate well with today's consumers and investors, who are increasingly demanding significant action on social and environmental issues.

Crafting a clear, consistent, and compelling CSR message that resonates across different audiences, cultures, and media is a challenging but essential task[14]. Businesses must ensure that their CSR communication is tailored to diverse stakeholder groups while maintaining a coherent narrative that reflects the company's core values and mission. This strategic approach not only builds trust and loyalty but also enhances the overall brand reputation in the competitive market of Sri Lanka.

Influence of Socio-Economic Factors

Socio-economic factors significantly influence consumer awareness and perceptions of CSR initiatives in Sri Lanka. In a study aimed at understanding corporate social responsibility (CSR) practices within the country, it was observed that these factors play a pivotal role in shaping how consumers interpret and value CSR efforts by companies. The research included a sample from the largest 200 companies listed on the Colombo Stock Exchange and utilized various statistical methods to analyze data collected through a questionnaire survey[15].

The study found that the size, ownership, and geographical scale of a business influence its CSR activities, which in turn affect consumer perceptions[15]. Larger companies with more extensive operations tend to have higher levels of CSR engagement, thereby increasing consumer awareness and positive perceptions of their brand[15]. The Kruskal–Wallis one-way ANOVA and Mann–Whitney U tests indicated significant variations in CSR activities based on these factors, highlighting the diverse impact of socio-economic conditions on consumer behavior[15].

Environmental and socially related activities of companies were measured using the Environmental Activity Percentage Score (EAPS) and Socially related Activity Percentage Score (SAPS), respectively[15]. Companies with higher scores in these areas are perceived more favorably by consumers, who are becoming increasingly aware of and concerned about environmental sustainability and social welfare[15]. Thus, socio-economic factors not only influence the extent to which companies engage in CSR but also shape consumer perceptions and expectations regarding corporate responsibility in Sri Lanka[15].

Successful CSR Initiatives

Sri Lanka has seen a number of successful Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives that have significantly influenced consumer perceptions and enhanced brand reputation. Sampath Bank, for instance, has been at the forefront of pioneering CSR initiatives and sustainability efforts in the banking sector. The bank achieved three prestigious awards at The Asia Sustainability Excellence Awards 2015 for the ‘Best Sustainability Report’ and at the Asia Best CSR Practices Awards for ‘Best Use of CSR Practices in Banking and Finance’ and ‘Poverty Alleviation’[16].

Coca-Cola Sri Lanka, in collaboration with Clean Ocean Force, launched “The Ocean

Guardian” programme as an extension of their “Adopt-A-Beach” initiative. This project involved community efforts in cleaning up beaches while promoting responsible waste management and coastal preservation, thus resonating well with consumers who value environmental responsibility[18].

The Gammadda initiative stands out as the largest CSR effort in the country in terms of reach and variety. Funded by compassionate viewers and corporations, this project addresses essential needs like access to clean water, housing, and better school facilities, thereby making a tangible impact on underserved communities[19].

CIC’s ‘Manussakama’ programme, launched in 2008, focuses on uplifting rural agricultural communities. Its flagship event, ‘CIC Soora Goviya,’ recognized and rewarded young agricultural entrepreneurs, thereby positively reinforcing their potential in the agricultural industry and gaining significant local and international accolades[20].

Nestlé Lanka's commitment to sustainability was recognized at the Best Corporate Citizen Sustainability Awards 2021. The company won awards in several categories including Corporate Environmental Commitment and Environment Beyond Business, showcasing its efforts in environmental sustainability[21]. Similarly, Unilever Sri Lanka was acknowledged for its ‘100% Re-Aqua’ project that created a circular economy for water, among other sustainability projects, at the Best Corporate Citizen Sustainability Awards 2020[22].

These initiatives illustrate how well-structured and impactful CSR activities can resonate with consumers, fostering a positive brand image and contributing to long-term business success.

Common Mistakes in CSR Communication

One common mistake Sri Lankan companies make in communicating their CSR initiatives is focusing too much on superficial or one-off activities rather than embedding genuine social and environmental efforts into their core business strategies[23]. Glossy photos in annual reports showcasing donations or tree-planting events are often perceived as insufficient, especially when these activities are not tied to broader, more impactful corporate policies[25]. As a result, consumers may view these efforts as disingenuous or merely performative.

Another significant issue is the lack of consistency and transparency in sustainability reporting. Over the past three decades, sustainability reporting in Sri Lanka has been largely

voluntary, which has led to varying levels of disclosure and sometimes incomplete or non-comparable data[24]. This inconsistency can lead to consumer skepticism about the authenticity of a company's CSR claims.

Moreover, the failure to align CSR initiatives with the company's long-term business goals and the societal needs of the local community is another pitfall. Companies often do not adequately communicate how their CSR activities contribute to addressing specific social and environmental challenges unique to Sri Lanka[26]. This misalignment can result in initiatives that are seen as irrelevant or ineffective, further damaging consumer trust and brand reputation.

Influence of Cultural Values

In Sri Lanka, cultural values play a significant role in shaping consumer expectations and perceptions of corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives. These cultural values, deeply rooted in the country's socio-economic and religious fabric, impact brand loyalty and purchasing decisions.

Studies have indicated that Sri Lankan consumers are highly influenced by cultural norms and expectations when it comes to CSR activities. For instance, a study analyzing the CSR practices of 200 of the largest companies listed on the Colombo Stock Exchange found that both environmental and social activities are crucial components of CSR in Sri Lanka, reflecting the cultural emphasis on community and environmental stewardship[27]. This study highlighted that consumer expectations are closely tied to how companies engage in these activities, with a significant impact on brand loyalty.

Further qualitative research involving export garment manufacturers in Sri Lanka revealed that the national cultural context significantly supports the implementation of CSR initiatives. The research showed that consumer perceptions are influenced by the degree to which companies align their CSR efforts with cultural values, leading to increased brand loyalty[28]. This alignment with cultural expectations is vital for gaining consumer trust and loyalty.

Another study emphasized the importance of contextual factors in CSR reporting and practices, noting that many Western-centric theories do not fully capture the nuances of CSR in developing countries like Sri Lanka. It was found that understanding the local cultural context is essential for effective CSR implementation and for meeting consumer

expectations[29].

Moreover, the corporate culture within Sri Lankan businesses themselves also reflects and reinforces these broader societal values. Companies that actively engage in CSR are seen as contributing to social, economic, and political development, which resonates well with the cultural values of the community. This perception boosts the company's reputation and sustainability, further influencing consumer trust and loyalty[30][31].

Challenges in Aligning CSR with Consumer Expectations

Companies in Sri Lanka face a myriad of challenges when aligning their Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives with local consumer expectations. The transition from traditional Corporate Social Responsibility to a more encompassing Business and Human Rights approach signifies a notable shift in the landscape. Simple gestures like donating money to charities or planting trees are no longer sufficient. Companies are now expected to publicly address significant social and environmental issues, demonstrating a genuine commitment beyond mere image-building exercises[32].

The unique social and environmental challenges inherent in Sri Lanka necessitate a contextual approach to sustainability reporting. Global influences shape these efforts, but the local context and expectations of consumers require businesses to adapt their CSR initiatives accordingly[33]. The integrative social contracts theory provides insights into these drivers, highlighting the importance of understanding local dynamics when crafting CSR strategies.

An example of a company navigating these challenges is the John Keells Group, which launched a comprehensive Crisis Response Initiative through its CSR entity, the John Keells Foundation, during Sri Lanka's socio-economic crisis in early 2022. This initiative, implemented in collaboration with Group businesses across the island, focused on critical areas such as Health & Nutrition, Education, and Livelihood Development. The programmes aimed to address immediate community challenges while fostering long-term self-reliance[34].

Moreover, consumer perception plays a significant role in the success of CSR initiatives. Research indicates that the effectiveness of CSR practices can directly influence consumer purchase intentions, particularly in the fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) sector.

Multinational enterprises operating in Sri Lanka must navigate the nuanced expectations of Sri Lankan consumers, who may exhibit varying levels of ethnocentrism and sensitivity to CSR practices[35][36]. Aligning CSR initiatives with these consumer expectations requires a deep understanding of local values and a commitment to genuinely addressing social and environmental issues rather than superficial efforts.

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